

D3.3 Proceedings
from the
Summer school on biophotonics

Name of project: **Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern Slovakia (CasProt) No. 952333**

D3.3 Proceedings from the Summer school on biophotonics

Name of project: Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in
Eastern Slovakia (**CasProt**) No. 952333

Deliverable No:	D3.3. (D16)
Work package No. and title:	WP3 Early-stage researchers: joint summer schools and training
Task No. and title:	Summer school on biophotonics
Nature:	Report
Dissemination level:	Public
Lead Beneficiary:	UPJS
Author(s):	doc. Mgr. Gregor Bánó, PhD.; RNDr. Veronika Huntošová, PhD.; RNDr. Zuzana Jurašeková, PhD.
Date of publication:	31 July 2023

Task leader: doc. Mgr. Gregor Bánó, PhD.

WP leader: RNDr. Veronika Huntošová, PhD.

Project coordinator: doc. RNDr. Erik Sedlák, DrSc.

Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the authors. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Summer School on biophotonics was organized by doctoral school of P. J. Safarik University in Kosice (UPJS) and was held at the Department of biophysics (Institute of Physics, Faculty of Science, UPJS) and Center for interdisciplinary biosciences (Technology and Innovation Park, UPJS) from May 22nd to May 31st, 2023. The executive management and coordination of the school were in the hands of the Dpt. of Biophysics. An overall 10-day course provided participants with a comprehensive understanding of fundamentals and advanced methods of biophotonics. The program integrated practical laboratory trainings with lectures/theoretical knowledge delivered by Slovak and foreign researchers and invited experts in the field.

The primary focus of the Summer school was to introduce participant to the recent advances in biophotonic research and corresponding efficient techniques which open new possibilities of non-contact, high-speed, multi-dimensional measurements and precision imaging methods. The students had the opportunity to learn fundamentals of these techniques within a set of lectures dedicated to optical spectroscopy, imaging and time-resolved techniques. The students were also provided with dedicated lectures on Safety and Good Laboratory Practice, as well as Ethics Issues in biophotonics. The lectures were coherently supplemented with practical demonstrations of the respective experimental techniques. Moreover, the interdisciplinary teams (each of 4-5 students) were formed to develop their own experimental projects, related to the focus of the School. At the end of the summer school, the experimental projects were publicly defended by the students, and subsequently, the students were awarded with the Certificates of attendance.

The School of Biophotonics was attended by 14 PhD students from different Slovak Universities, the lectures and practical training were impacted by 10 (inter)nationally recognized experts in the field of biophotonics (invited foreign speakers include prof. H. van den Bergh, dr. G. Wagnieres and dr. S. Sanchez-Cortes; Slovak researchers and experts include prof. P. Miškovský, prof. A. Marček Chorvátová, dr. D. Chorvát, dr. G. Žoldák). All laboratory sessions were led by researchers working at the Department of biophysics and Center for interdisciplinary biosciences, namely Gregor Bánó, Zuzana Jurašeková and Veronika Huntošová.

In summary, the Summer school of biophotonics was highly acclaimed by all of the participants, as well as lecturers. The student's teams presented high-quality research projects that we believe can lead in future to new collaborations, proposals and research projects.

<http://www.biofyzika.sk/sk/event/114/summer-school-on-biophotonics-letna-skola-biofotoniky-2023>

<https://www.upjs.sk/pracoviska/tip/en/summer-school-on-biophotonics/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

TABLE OF CONTENT

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
TABLE OF CONTENT.....	4
1. Summer school programme.....	5
2. Overview of the lectures' content.....	6
3. Summer school trainings and experiments	12
Fluorescence imaging of cells and detection of oxidative stress response of cells.....	12
Raman spectroscopy	13
Time-resolved in-vitro detection of singlet oxygen produced in photodynamic processes	15
Microfluidics and optical tweezers.....	16
4. Students' presentations	17
APPENDIX 1. Students' protocols from fluorescence imaging and flow-cytometry measurements	51
APPENDIX 2. Photogallery	69
APPENDIX 3. Certificate of attendance.....	73

Summer School of Biophotonics 2023

22 - 31 May 2023, Košice

		9:00 - 10:15	break	10:30 - 11:45	lunch	14:00 - 15:00	break	15:15 - 16:00	16:00 - 17:00
1	Monday	22.5	Pavol Miškovičský <i>Repetition in optics and spectroscopy</i>	Gregor Bánó <i>Principles of optical experiments I.</i>		Gregor Bánó <i>Principles of optical experiments II.</i>		Safety	
2	Tuesday	23.5	Hubert van den Bergh <i>Photomedicine: detecting and treating diseases using light I.</i>	Hubert van den Bergh <i>Photomedicine: detecting and treating diseases using light II.</i>		Project 1-2-3 (Part 1)			
3	Wednesday	24.5	Georges Wagnieres <i>Radiometry/photometry, tissue optics and light dosimetry I.</i>	Georges Wagnieres <i>Radiometry/photometry, tissue optics and light dosimetry II.</i>		Project 1-2-3 (Part 2)			
4	Thursday	25.5	A. Marček Chorvátová <i>Fluorescence microscopy techniques and environmental applications I.</i>	A. Marček Chorvátová <i>Fluorescence microscopy techniques and environmental applications II.</i>		Project 1-2-3 (Part 3)			
5	Friday	26.5	S. Sanches-Cortes - online <i>Raman and Surface-enhanced optical spectroscopy</i>	Dušan Chorvát - online <i>Advanced laser imaging techniques</i>		social event			
6	Saturday	27.5	training in microfluidics and optical tweezers						
7	Sunday	28.5	self studies, work on presentations						
8	Monday	29.5	Zuzana Jurašeková <i>SERS applications</i>	Gabriel Žoldák <i>Single-molecule force spectroscopy using optical tweezers</i>		Project 1-2-3 (Part 3)			
9	Tuesday	30.5	company presentation						
10	Wednesday	31.5	project presentations, closing						

project 1 cell cultures, microscopy (Veronika Huntošová, Zuzana Naďová)

project 2 Raman spectroscopy, SERS (Zuzana Jurašeková, Paulína Slepčíková/Annamária Jutková)

project 3 singlet oxygen detection (Gregor Bánó, Andrej Hovan)

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N 952333

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

2. Overview of the lectures' content

LECTURE 1.

Introduction (repetitorium in optics and spectroscopy)

prof. P. Miškovský (P. J. Šafárik University in Košice, Slovakia)

- Fundamentals of Biophotonics.
 - Basic characteristics of optical radiation, polarization, reflection, refraction, interference, diffraction and diffusion of light.
 - Basics principles of light interaction with matter.
 - Basic principles of optical spectroscopy (absorption and emission spectroscopy, light scattering).
-

LECTURE 2.

Principles of optical experiments

dr. G. Bánó (P. J. Šafárik University in Košice, Slovakia)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Part 1.

- Light sources in optical spectroscopy and microscopy.
- Principles of laser physics.

Part 2.

- Physical principles of optical signal detection (Photomultipliers, photodiodes, CMOS and CCD cameras).
 - Optical design in theory and practice (optical elements, optomechanical components).
 - Principles of image formation in light microscopy.
 - Laser safety.
-

LECTURE 3.

Photomedicine: detecting and treating diseases using light

prof. Hubert van den Bergh (EPFL, Lausanne, Switzerland)

Four examples of developing drugs and instruments “from the laboratory to the hospital“:

Part 1.

- Photodynamic treatment of small cancers in the mouth, lungs and oesophagus: the development of the drug FOSCAN.
- Autofluorescence detection of small cancers in the lungs: the development of the bronchoscope DAFE.

Part 2.

- Fluorescence for detecting and removing cancers of the bladder: the development of the drug HEXVIX.
 - Treating age-related macular degeneration and ocular polyps: the development of the drug VISUDYNE.
-

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

LECTURE 4.

Radiometry and photometry

MER dr. Georges Wagnières (EPFL, Lausanne, Switzerland)

Part 1.

- Optical parameters characterizing tissues.
- Unit systems in radiometry and photometry.
- In-class exercises.

Part 2.

- Tissue optics.
- Light dosimetry in biological tissues.
- In-class exercises.

LECTURE 5.

Fluorescence microscopy techniques and environmental applications

prof. Alžbeta Marček Chorvátová, DrSc. (UCM, Trnava, Slovakia)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Part 1.

- Light interaction with molecules.
- Light sources, lasers and laser applications.
- Different microscopes and microscopy techniques.

Part 2.

- Fluorescence probes and proteins.
- Cell culture and cell function imaging.
- Light-tissue interaction.
- Environmental applications.

LECTURE 6.

Raman and surface-enhanced optical spectroscopy

dr. S. Sánchez-Cortés (IEM CSIC, Madrid, Spain)

Raman spectroscopy

- Theoretical background of Raman effect.
- Methods of Raman spectroscopy (classical, resonance, ...).
- Bioapplications.

Surface-enhanced optical spectroscopies

- Introduction to Plasmonics.
- Surface-enhanced optical spectroscopies (SERS – Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy; SEF – Surface-enhanced fluorescence; SEIRA – Surface-enhanced infrared absorption).
- Enhancement mechanisms on plasmonic nanoparticles.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

- Nanofabrication and functionalization of nanoparticles.
-

LECTURE 7.

Advanced laser imaging techniques

Dr. Dušan Chorvát (ILC, Bratislava, Slovakia)

- Principles of nonlinear optics.
 - SHG and 2-photon microscopy.
 - Super-resolution microscopy techniques.
 - Fluorescence lifetime imaging (FLIM).
 - Fluorescence resonant energy transfer (FRET).
-

LECTURE 8.

Single-molecule force spectroscopy using optical tweezers

Dr. Gabriel Žoldák (P. J. Šafárik University in Košice, Slovakia)

- The history of optical tweezers development.
 - Different optical tweezer arrangements.
 - The theoretical background of optical trapping.
 - Review of optical trapping applications.
 - Experimental methods of single protein force spectroscopy using optical tweezers.
 - Selected application examples.
-

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

SERS application

dr. Z. Jurašeková (P. J. Šafárik University in Košice, Slovakia)

- Repetitorium of Raman and SERS spectroscopy.
 - Raman mapping and imaging.
 - Raman set-up.
 - Material characterization.
 - Cultural heritage applications.
 - Molecular paleobiology applications
 - Selective and sensitive detection of trace concentrations of pollutants.
 - Bioapplications (e.g., drug-ligand interactions, biosensors, Raman imaging of cells and tissues).
-

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

3. Summer school trainings and experiments

TRAINING 1.

Fluorescence imaging of cells and detection of oxidative stress response of cells

dr. V. Huntošová

Goal:

Introduction to basics of microscopy, fluorescence microscopy and confocal fluorescence microscopy. Detection of cell viability and separation of cell populations by flow-cytometry will be introduced as well.

Description:

Students will prepare cell culture samples for different techniques of imaging and analysis of cell metabolism. Immunostaining and vital staining samples will be prepared for fluorescence imaging. Cells will be treated with different molecules to induce acute oxidative stress. MTT-assay of viability and flow-cytometry for uptake of molecules by cells will be used. Students will be trained in detection techniques, analysis of images and distribution plots from flow-cytometry, presentation of results. At the end of the course, student will elaborate protocols for imaging and flow-cytometry measurements.

(**Note:** The students' protocols are presented in Appendix 1.)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Raman spectroscopy

dr. Z. Jurašková

Goal:

Introduction to Raman spectroscopy (to understand principles of dispersive Raman instrument) and optimization of Raman experiment for the best possible results. Demonstration of SERS spectroscopy as an important analytical technique.

Description:

Principles of Raman and SERS spectroscopy will be explained through the particular measurements:

1. Registration of Raman spectra of different samples (solid/liquid; inorganic/organic) – optimization of instrument and software setting for the best possible results (macro/micro mode, laser power, exposure time, accumulations).
2. Data processing and simple analysis. Illustrative interpretation of the registered Raman spectra – basic vibrational assignments. Post-registration manipulation of the data (cosmic rays, peak pick, baseline subtraction, etc.).
3. Effect of different experimental conditions: wavelength of the excitation line, type of colloid, concentration, pH, etc.
4. SERS experiments (fluorescence quenching, signal enhancement, detection limit, affinity of the molecule towards different SERS substrates, different experimental conditions, impurities).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Preparation for SERS experiments:

- I. Preparation of active SERS substrates using metal colloids.
- II. Characterization of metal colloids by UV-Vis and Raman Spectroscopy (absorption maximum – plasmon resonance, fwhm – particle size distribution, aggregation – activation of SERS substrates, anomalous bands, effect of pH, ...).

Materials:

In this training, the experimental setup present in the Laboratory of Raman spectroscopy at the Department of biophysics will be used. There is no need of any special sample preparation. Silver and gold colloids will be prepared by chemical reduction. All the glass materials have to be previously cleaned using chromic solution and rinsed several times with tri-distilled water.

Special issues:

Raman spectroscopy also possesses desirable properties for imaging applications, such as chemical specificity, high spatial resolution, low background signal, any or little sample preparation, etc. This technique will be of interest to better understand the distribution of components within the samples.

Time-resolved in-vitro detection of singlet oxygen produced in photodynamic processes

dr. G. Bánó

Goal:

To learn about time-resolved laser spectroscopy techniques and to perform time-resolved singlet oxygen phosphorescence and transient absorption measurements. Students will gain an understanding of optical apparatus construction as well as theoretical background and data evaluation methods related to molecular photo-kinetics.

Description:

Phosphorescence of singlet oxygen at 1270 nm will be measured following pulsed laser excitation of photosensitizer solutions placed in a cuvette. The time-resolved signal from a PMT will be collected in photon counting mode using a multichannel scaler/averager. At the same time the lifetime of the triplet state photosensitizer will be measured in a transient absorption experiment. Students will learn the theory behind the kinetics of triplet and singlet molecular states involved. The lifetimes of the photosensitizer triplet state and singlet oxygen will be evaluated by fitting the experimental data with the theoretical time-dependence. The experiments will be carried out at different oxygen concentrations.

Materials: photosensitizers (RuPhen, FMN - flavin-mononucleotide), oxygen gas.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Microfluidics and optical tweezers

dr. G. Bánó

Goal:

To demonstrate the fundamental principles of a Raman tweezers setup and to provide an introduction to the construction of microfluidic devices.

Description:

Participants will gain insight into the design of basic laser tweezers equipment. They will test the theoretical basics of optical micromanipulation in practice. A simple microfluidic device made of PDMS will be prepared and used to trap single yeast cells using an optical tweezers apparatus.

Materials: polystyrene and silica micro-beads, yeast cells, PDMS.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

4. Students' presentations

PRESENTATION 1.

Determination of the limits of detection (LODs) of selected pesticides using SERS spectroscopy

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Stanovenie limitu detekcie (LOD) pesticídov metódou Ramanovej/SERS spektroskopie

Iuliia Baglaeva, Viktória Čákyová, Alexandra Gubóová, Dominik Michálek, Veronika Niščáková

Coordinator:

Cooperating partners:

Pod vedením: RNDr. Zuzana Jurašková, PhD.

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

CasProt

Ramanova spektroskopia (RS)

- patrí medzi spektroskopické metódy, ktoré využívajú na štúdium štruktúry vibračné a rotačné stavy molekúl
- funguje na neelastickom (Ramanovom) rozptyle monochromatického žiarenia na molekulách študovanej látky

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

2 CasProt

Princíp RS

- žiarenie lasera prevedie skúmanú molekulu do vyššieho energetického stavu- vibračného alebo rotačného;
- pri relaxácii sa vráti späť do základného stavu, ale do inej energetickej hladiny (iný vibračný, rotačný stav) pričom vyžiari žiarenie, ktoré má vlnovú dĺžku posunutú o hodnotu energie odpovedajúcej danému rotačnému alebo vibračnému stavu.

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

3 CasProt

- molekula je v Ramanovom spektre aktívna, ak je polarizovateľná; má dipólový moment;
- čím vyššia je polarizovateľnosť molekuly, tým vyššia je intenzita Ramanovho žiarenia;
- existujú dva typy Ramanovho rozptylu, ktoré sa navzájom dopĺňajú – Stokesov (odpovedá rotačnej excitácii) a Anti-Stokesov (odpovedá rotačnej relaxácii) rozptyl;
- zdroj monochromatického žiarenia = lasery (najčastejšie VIS alebo IR ale aj blízka UV).

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

4 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Povrchovo-zosilnená RS (SERS)

- povrchovo citlivá metóda;
- výsledkom je zosilnený Ramanov rozptyl molekúl, ktoré sú adsorbované na zdrsnených kovových povrchoch;
- medzi najčastejšie používané kovy patria Au, Ag a zriedkavejšie Cu, Pt, Pd.

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

5 CasProt

Povrchovo-zosilnená RS (SERS)

- "Hot spots" medzi časticami
- pri SERS technike sa využívajú **drsné povrchy** alebo **nanočastice**
- Koloidné nanočastice striebra/zlata

👉 Detekcia jednej molekuly

K zosilneniu Ramanovho signálu adsorbovaných molekúl dochádza na špecifických povrchoch v dôsledku zosilnenia elektrického poľa zabezpečeného povrchom.

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

6 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Motivácia

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

7

Experimentálna časť

• Použitý materiál:

- Koloid AgH
- KNO_3
- DT8 (1,8-oktánditiol)
- Pesticídy: Aldrín, Dieldrín, Endrín

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

8

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Postup a metodika práce

- I. Příprava zásobných roztokov študovaných molekúl
- II. Nastavenie experimentálnych podmienok – optimalizácia: Ramanove a SERS spektrá merané pri λ_{exc} : 633 nm, 532 nm, 785 nm
- III. SERS merania – koncentračné závislosti – výpočet limitu detekcie (LOD)

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

9 CasProt

Výsledky

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

10 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

11 CasProt

Limit detekcie

- Limit detekcie je najnižší signál alebo najnižšia zodpovedajúca veličina, ktorú sa má zo signálu určiť, ktorú možno pozorovať s dostatočnou mierou spoľahlivosti alebo štatistickej významnosti.

$$[LOD] = (3\sigma - a) / b$$

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

12 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Názov	Aldrín	Endrín	Dieldrín
a	0,47666	0,18244	0,69811
b	2,15951	245187	6,03185
σ	0,25291	0,17988	0,27143
R ²	0,9802	0,9793	0,9706
LOD	48 ppb	555 ppb	7,3 ppb

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

13 CasProt

Záver

- Detekcia a stanovenie pesticídov je veľmi dôležité, nakoľko pesticídy predstavujú dlhodobé nebezpečenstvo pre životné prostredie
- SERS = efektívna, časovo a finančne nenáročná, priamočiara analytická technika na monitorovanie prítomnosti (kvalitatívne) a množstva (kvantitatívne) molekúl v analyzovaných vzorkách
- LOD = najmenšie množstvo analyzovanej látky, ktoré možno spoľahlivo zistiť danou metódou

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

14 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

asProt

Ďakujeme za pozornosť!
Thank you!

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

15 asProt

asProt

Any questions?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

PRESENTATION 2.

Imaging of cells and detection of oxidative stress effect

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Imaging of cells and detection of oxidative stress effect

Mgr. Veronika Demčáková, Mgr. Viktória Fedorová, RNDr. Cyril Slabý, Mgr. Monika Štulajterová, Mgr. Adriána Tomková

Coordinator:

Cooperating partners:

Supervision: RNDr. Veronika Huntosova, PhD.

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

CasProt

Outline

1. **Inhibition effect of cisplatin**
 - glioblastoma cells, cisplatin, cell counting
2. **Photodynamic therapy**
 - Jurkat cells, MTT assay (hypericin, formazan)
3. **Determination of the oxidative stress in cells using a confocal microscope**
 - fluorescent dye (Mitotracker), glioblastoma cells
4. **Determination of the oxidative stress in cells using a flow cytometry**
 - Jurkat cells, 5-fluorouracil, fluorescence

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

2 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Experiment 1: Inhibition effect of cisplatin

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

3 CasProt

Glioblastoma

- The most aggressive and most common type of cancer that originates in the brain
- Symptoms of glioblastoma may include headaches, personality changes, nausea, and symptoms similar to those of a stroke
- The cause of most cases of glioblastoma is not known
- Treatment usually involves surgery, after which chemotherapy and radiation therapy are used

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

4 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Cisplatin

- Cisplatin was discovered in 1845 and licensed for medical use in 1978 and 1979
- Chemotherapy medication used to treat a number of cancers
- Cisplatin interferes with DNA replication, which kills the fastest proliferating cells, which in theory are cancerous
- Common side effects include bone marrow suppression, hearing problems, including total irreversible hearing loss, usually restricted to one ear, kidney damage, and vomiting

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

5 CasProt

Cell counting

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

6 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

1 hour

12 hours

24 hours

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

7 CasProt

Experiment 2: Photodynamic therapy

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

8 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Jurkat cells

- suspension T-lymphoblasts of acute lymphoblastic leukemia, the most common oncological disease of children,
- express surface receptors, such as the T-cell receptor (TCR), CD3, and CD28,
- immortalized cell line, they can divide indefinitely in culture, making them a valuable tool for studying various aspects of T cell biology,
- have different cytoskeletal dynamics than Primary T-cells (actin looks different),
- they have been used to investigate viral replication, host-virus interactions, and the development of antiviral drugs,
- diameter: 10-16 μm

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

9 CasProt

MTT assay

- colorimetric assay for assessing cell metabolic activity
- MTT, a yellow tetrazole, is reduced to purple formazan in living cells
- photosensitizer : hypericine

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

10 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Jurkat cells

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

11 CasProt

Experiment 3: Determination of the oxidative stress in cells using a confocal microscope

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

12 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Confocal microscopy

- patented in 1957 by Marvin Minsky
- used in the characterization of the surface of microstructured materials
- an optical imaging technique for increasing optical resolution and contrast of a micrograph
- confocal microscope only focuses a smaller beam of light at one narrow depth level at a time

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

13 CasProt

U87MG - Glioblastoma

a) Hoechst

b) CM-TMRos (MitoTracker Dye)

c) Hoechst + CM-TMRos

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

14 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Experiment 4: Determination of the oxidative stress in cells using a flow cytometry

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

15

casProt

Flow cytometry

- A laser-based technique used to analyze multiple physical and chemical characteristics of cells or particles
- Measurements:
 - Forward scatter - FSC (size)
 - Side scatter - SSC (granularity / internal complexity)
 - Emitted fluorescence (fluorescence intensity)

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

16

casProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

5-fluorouracil

- A cytotoxic chemotherapy medication used to treat cancer
- Fluorouracil is in the antimetabolite and pyrimidine analog families of medications.

Figure 3. The excitation fluorescence spectra of the non-irradiated 5-FU solution and the irradiated 5-FU solutions with N₂ laser beam.

Figure 4. The emission fluorescence spectra of the non-irradiated and irradiated 5-FU solutions with N₂ laser beam.

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

17 CasProt

Characterization of Jurkat cells

- Cells (CM-TMRos):
 - K Jurkat
 - A1 Jurkat + nanoparticles
 - A1 5-FU Jurkat + nanoparticles + 5-fluorouracil
 - 5-FU Jurkat + 5-fluorouracil
- Measurements:
 - Forward scatter
 - Side scatter
 - Fluorescence:
 - 405 nm - 450/50 nm
 - 488 nm - 585/40 nm

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

18 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Forward/Side scatter

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

19 CasProt

Fluorescence

- Excitation: 405 nm
- Emission: 450/50 nm

- Excitation: 488 nm
- Emission: 585/40 nm

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

20 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

asProt

Thank you!

doc. Mgr. Gregor Bánó, PhD.

RNDr. Zuzana Jurašková, PhD.

RNDr. Veronika Huntošová, PhD.

30.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

21

asProt

asProt

Any questions?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

PRESENTATION 3.

Singlet oxygen detection/Detekcia singletového kyslíka

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Singlet oxygen detection/Detekcia singletového stavu kyslíka

RNDr. Viktória Pevná, Mgr. Kristína Felčíková, Mgr. Majlinda Meta, Mgr. Jana Sabová

Coordinator:

Cooperating partners:

Supervision: doc. Mgr. Gregor Bánó, PhD.

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

asProt

Jablonského diagram

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

2 asProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Experimentálna aparatúra

Nd:YAG (1064 nm) –
OPO laditeľné
He-Ne (633 nm) –
kontinuálny

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

3 asProt

Experimentálna aparatúra

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

4 asProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

RuPhen

- dichlorotrís(1,10-phenantrothrolíne) ruthenium hydrate
- hydrofilný
- využívaný na *in vivo* detekciu kyslíka
- vysoká termosenzitivita, vysoká intenzita luminiscencie
- antitumorigénny a virostatický
- kvantový výťažok produkcie singletového kyslíka RuPhenu rozpusteného v 0,9% vodnom roztoku NaCl – meraný pri rôznych teplotách a koncentráciách kyslíka

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

5 CasProt

Flavínmononukleotid (FMN)

- z riboflavínu (vitamín B2)
- 2 absorpčné maximá: 374 nm a 446 nm
- prostetická skupina rôznych oxidoreduktáz, kofaktor v biologických fotoreceptoroch
- izoaloxazínová skupina, ribitolová skupina, fosfátová skupina

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

6 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Meranie č.1

- 5 μM RuPhen v H_2O , 20% kyslíka

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

7 CasProt

Meranie č.2

- 5 μM RuPhen v H_2O , 100% kyslíka

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

8 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Meranie č.2

- 5 μM RuPhen v H_2O , 20% a 100% kyslíka

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

9 asProt

Meranie č.2

- 5 μM RuPhen v H_2O , po 20 min

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

10 asProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Tranzientná absorpcia

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

11 CasProt

Meranie č.3

- 5 μM FMN v H_2O , 20% kyslíka, tranzientná absorpcia

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

12 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Meranie č.4

- 5 μM FMN v H_2O , 100% kyslíka, tranzientná absorpcia

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

13 CasProt

Zhrnutie

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

14 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Singletový kyslík

- Základný stav kyslíka-tripletový
- $^1\text{O}_2$
- reaktívna forma kyslíka
- Fosforescencia pri 1270 nm

State	Orbital Assignment
$^1\Sigma_g^+$	$\uparrow_{\pi} \downarrow_{\pi}$
$^1\Delta_g$	$\uparrow\downarrow_{\pi} \circ_{\pi}$
$^3\Sigma_g^-$	$\uparrow_{\pi} \uparrow_{\pi}$

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

15 CasProt

Schéma experimentálnej aparatúry

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

16 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Meranie č.1

- 5 μM FMN v H_2O

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

17 CasProt

Meranie č.2

- 5 μM FMN v D_2O

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

18 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Zhrnutie

FMN	Doba života tripletu	Doba života singletu
V H ₂ O	2,3 μs	4,016 μs
V D ₂ O	2,3 μs	15,9 μs

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

19 CasProt

Hypericin

- Ľubovník bodkovaný
- antivírusový a nešpecifický inhibitor kinázy
- akumulácia v rakovinových bunkách

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

20 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Meranie č.3

- Hypericín v DMSO

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

21 CasProt

Meranie č.4

- Hypericín v DMSO (2 ml) + H₂O (1 ml)

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

22 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Zhrnutie

$$[\Delta] = \frac{K}{\tau_T - \tau_\Delta} \left(e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_T}} - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_\Delta}} \right)$$

Hypericín	Doba života tripletu	Doba života singletu
DMSO	1,6 µs	9,9 µs
DMSO + H ₂ O	1,3 µs	9,15 µs

31.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

23 CasProt

CasProt

Thank you!

30.05.2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

24 CasProt

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

APPENDIX 1. Students' protocols from fluorescence imaging and flow-cytometry measurements

PROTOCOL OF GROUP 1.

Iuliia Baglaeva, Viktoria Cakyova, Alexandra Guboova, Dominik Michalek, Veronika Niscakova

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Fluorescence immunostaining of cell cultures

Figure 1: Illustrative images of A) immunostained cells and B) decomposition of detected RGB (red-green-blue) channels.

1. Cells (30 000 cells per dish) are seeded in Petri dishes with coverslips for confocal fluorescence microscopy. When cells reach a confluent layer, the samples are treated with tested substances that affect cell metabolism.
2. 24 hours after treatment the cells are fixed with 3.7 % paraformaldehyde for 7 minutes. The samples are then 3x washed with cold phosphate buffer saline (PBS) pH 7.4.
3. In the next step the cells are penetrated for 5 minutes by $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ acetone/methanolic solution (1:1 w/w) at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to allow antibodies to reach the targets. The samples are rinsed 3x with cold PBS pH 7.4.
4. To block nonspecific binding of primary antibodies, the samples are incubated for 1 hour in 5 % bovine serum albumin (BSA)/skimmed milk solution at room temperature. The samples are rinsed 3x with cold PBS pH 7.4.
5. Primary antibodies diluted in 2.5 % BSA/glycine/Tween20 solution are incubated with samples for 1 hour at room temperature or alternatively overnight at $8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The samples are rinsed 3x with cold PBS pH 7.4.
6. Secondary (fluorescent) antibodies diluted in 1 % BSA solution are selected according to primary antibodies and incubated for 1 hour at room temperature in the dark. The samples are rinsed 3x with cold PBS pH 7.4. The second wash step is enriched with Hoechst to counter-stain nuclei of the cells.
7. Cells are mounted with mounting medium and kept in the dark until microscopy.

Primary antibody: Beta-actin (anti rabbit); Cytochrome C (anti mouse)

Secondary antibody: Alexa Fluor 405; Alexa Fluor 546

Excitation: a) 405 nm (blue)

 b) 555 nm (red)

Emission: a) 400 nm -555 nm

 b) 559 nm →

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Figure 2: The information about excitation and emission from the software

Observation:

We used antibodies to visualize the localization of specific organelles in individual cells based on their emitted light using a confocal microscope.

Blue- Hoechst 33342 – nucleus

Red- MitoTracker Orange – mitochondria

Cells under white light:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Mitochondria- red- progress of oxidative stress caused by irradiation: The red colour gradually reached nucleuses.

Nuclei- blue:

Nuclei and mitochondria:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Treatment:

Cell clusters under white light:

Cell clusters:

Layers:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

11 successive layer-by-layer scans were performed, on the basis of which we can create a 3D image of the observed structure.

Flow-cytometric analysis of treated cells

Figure 1: Illustrative images of A) histograms of fluorescence intensities distributed in cell population and B) correlation plots of fluorescence parameters.

1. Cells (30 000 cells per dish) are seeded in Petri dishes (3.5 cm in diameter). When cells reach a confluent layer, the samples are treated with tested substances that affect cell metabolism.
2. 24 hours after treatment the cells are detached from petri dish with Trypsin and centrifuged (1200 rpm for 5 minutes) to collect cell pellets.
3. In the next step the cell pellets are resuspended in Annexin V binding buffer (0.5 ml) supplemented with Annexin V/FITC that binds to phosphatidyl serine expressed on cell surface of apoptotic cells. Samples are incubated for 15 minutes.
4. Propidium iodide stains nuclei of late apoptotic and necrotic cells. PI is added to samples prior the measurement.

Excitation: a) 405 nm

b) 488 nm

Emission: a) 450±50 nm

b) 585±40 nm

Observation:

Flow cytometry is a technique that detects chemical/physical characteristics of a population of cells and measures them. This technique helps to visualize individual parameters statistically, however, is unable to localize them. Histograms show fluorescence on x axis and normalized number of cells on y axis.

Cells without Hoechst, but already damaged by previous analysis.

The overlap is caused by having same parameters, but of different origin. Orange curve is shifted because of damage caused by previous irradiation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

PROTOCOL OF GROUP 2.

Adriána Tomková, Veronika Demčáková, Monika Štulajterová, Viktória Fedorová, Cyril Slabý

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Fluorescence immunostaining of cell cultures

Figure 1: Illustrative images of A) immunostained cells and B) decomposition of detected RGB (red-green-blue) channels.

1. Cells (30 000 cells per dish) are seeded in Petri dishes with coverslips for confocal fluorescence microscopy. When cells reach a confluent layer, the samples are treated with tested substances that affect cell metabolism.
2. 24 hours after treatment the cells are fixed with 3.7 % paraformaldehyde for 7 minutes. The samples are then 3x washed with cold phosphate buffer saline (PBS) pH 7.4.
3. In the next step the cells are penetrated for 5 minutes by $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ acetone/methanolic solution (1:1 w/w) at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to allow antibodies to reach the targets. The samples are rinsed 3x with cold PBS pH 7.4.
4. To block nonspecific binding of primary antibodies, the samples are incubated for 1 hour in 5 % bovine serum albumin (BSA)/skimmed milk solution at room temperature. The samples are rinsed 3x with cold PBS pH 7.4.
5. Primary antibodies diluted in 2.5 % BSA/glycine/Tween20 solution are incubated with samples for 1 hour at room temperature or alternatively overnight at $8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The samples are rinsed 3x with cold PBS pH 7.4.
6. Secondary (fluorescent) antibodies diluted in 1 % BSA solution are selected according to primary antibodies and incubated for 1 hour at room temperature in the dark. The samples are rinsed 3x with cold PBS pH 7.4. The second wash step is enriched with Hoechst to counter-stain nuclei of the cells.
7. Cells are mounted with mounting medium and kept in the dark until microscopy.

Primary antibody: Beta-actin (anti rabbit); Cytochrome C (anti mouse)

Secondary antibody: Alexa Fluor 405; Alexa Fluor 546

Excitation: 405 nm; 555 nm

Emission: 400-555 nm; 559 nm LP

Observation: We used immunofluorescence technique for visualization of certain components in cells. For this method we used indirect immunostaining, in which the primary antibody recognized and bound to the target biomolecule and secondary antibody with fluorescence dye was targeted against the primary one. After fluorophores excitation we could visualize the location of the antibodies in cells.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Figure 2. Glioblastoma cell culture incubated with cisplatin after A) 1 hour, B) 12 hours, C) 24 hours

Figure 3. Incubation curve of glioblastoma cells incubated with Cisplatin after 24 hours.

Figure 4. Fluorescence staining of glioblastoma cells with A) Hoechst (nucleus), B) CM-TMRos (mitochondria), C) Hoechst + CM-TMRos.

Flow-cytometric analysis of treated cells

Figure 1: Illustrative images of A) histograms of fluorescence intensities distributed in cell population and B) correlation plots of fluorescence parameters.

1. Cells (30 000 cells per dish) are seeded in Petri dishes (3.5 cm in diameter). When cells reach a confluent layer, the samples are treated with tested substances that affect cell metabolism.
2. 24 hours after treatment the cells are detached from petri dish with Trypsin and centrifuged (1200 rpm for 5 minutes) to collect cell pellets.
3. In the next step the cell pellets are resuspended in Annexin V binding buffer (0.5 ml) supplemented with Annexin V/FITC that binds to phosphatidyl serine expressed on cell surface of apoptotic cells. Samples are incubated for 15 minutes.
4. Propidium iodide stains nuclei of late apoptotic and necrotic cells. PI is added to samples prior the measurement.

Excitation: 405 nm, 488 nm

Emission: 450/50 nm, 585/40 nm

Observation:

We used flow cytometry technique to measure oxidative stress in Jurkat cells incubated for 24 hours. We measured 3 different samples: Jurkat cells incubated with nanoparticles; Jurkat cells incubated with nanoparticle and 5-fluorouracil; Jurkat cells incubated with 5-fluorouracil. As a control we used pure Jurkat cells. At emission spectra at 450/50 nm we could observe visible shift in the presence of 5-fluorouracil because of its fluorescence. Another peak appears near intensity 10^2 in samples containing nanoparticles, which are able to emit blue light (Figure 2B). We conclude that there is a small shift in spectra intensity at 585/40 nm in samples incubated with 5-fluorouracil due to higher oxidative stress (Figure 2C).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Figure 2: Flow cytometry graphs of groups of Jurkat cells (orange - control Jurkat, pink – Jurkat + nanoparticles, blue – Jurkat + nanoparticles + 5-fluorouracil, green – Jurkat + 5-fluorouracil) – A) dot blot of forward scatter (FSC) vs. side scatter (SSC); B) fluorescence emission spectra at 450/50 nm; C) fluorescence emission spectra at 585/40 nm; D) dot blot of fluorescence emission spectra 585/40 nm vs. 450/50 nm.

PROTOCOL OF GROUP 3.

Viktória Pevná, Kristína Felčíková, Majlinda Meta, Jana Sabová

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Fluorescence immunostaining of cell cultures

Figure 1: Illustrative images of A) immunostained cells and B) decomposition of detected RGB (red-green-blue) channels.

1. Cells (30 000 cells per dish) are seeded in Petri dishes with coverslips for confocal fluorescence microscopy. When cells reach a confluent layer, the samples are stained with dyes to visualize the localization of specific organelles in individual cells based on their emitted light using a confocal fluorescence microscope.

Excitation: a) 405 nm (blue)

b) 555 nm (red)

Emission: a) 400 nm -555 nm

b) 559 nm →

Observation:

We used antibodies to visualize the localization of specific organelles in individual cells based on their emitted light using a confocal microscope.

Blue- Hoechst 33342 – nucleus

Red- MitoTracker Orange – mitochondria

Figure 2: Cells (cell line U87MG) under white light:

Mitochondria- red- progress of oxidative stress caused by irradiation: The red colour gradually reached nucleuses.

Figure 3: Mitochondria- red, : The red colour gradually reached nucleuses.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Figure 4: Nuclei- blue

Figure 5: Nuclei and mitochondria

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Figure 6: Successive layer-by-layer scans were performed, on the basis of which we can create a 3D image of the observed structure.

Figure 7: 3D image of observed cells

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Flow-cytometric analysis of treated cells

Figure 1: Illustrative images of A) histograms of fluorescence intensities distributed in cell population and B) correlation plots of fluorescence parameters.

1. Cells (Jurkat cell line) are seeded in Petri dishes (3.5 cm in diameter). When cells reach desired confluency, the samples are collected
2. In the next step the cell are resuspended in cell medium and divided into five working groups. Control group (not stained), cells stained with Mitotracker orange, cells stained with hoechst, cells stained with hoechst and mitotracker combined, cell treated with H2O2 and stained with mitotracker orange. Samples are incubated for 15 minutes.

Observation:

Flow cytometry is a technique that detects chemical/physical characteristics of a population of cells and measures them. This technique helps to visualize individual parameters statistically, however, is unable to localize them. Histograms show fluorescence on x axis and normalized number of cells on y axis. H2O2 in the experiment was used to induce oxidation stress in the cells.

- A) Histogram of whole population of cells. B) Black- control group, Orange- cells+mitotracker orange, purple- cells+ Hoechst and mitotracker, blue- cells + Hoechst, red- cells+ H2O2 and mitotracker orange. C) Histogram of divided cell population into groups based on their staining with dyes, colors corresponds with groups same as in the picture B.

APPENDIX 2. Photogallery

The school participants:

In the lecture room:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

In the labs:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Breaktime:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

Social event, visiting Levoca and the Spis Castle:

Certificates of attendance award:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

APPENDIX 3. Certificate of attendance

PAVOL JOZEF ŠAFÁRIK UNIVERSITY IN KOŠICE
Faculty of Science

P. J. Šafárik University, Faculty of Science
Department of Biophysics
Košice, Slovak Republic

Certificate of attendance

PARTICIPANT'S NAME AND SURNAME

attended

School of Biophotonics

Theoretical Courses

Introduction (repetitorium in optics and spectroscopy) * Principles of optical experiments
* Time-resolved fluorescence techniques * Fluorescence microscopy techniques *
Vibrational (Raman and IR) spectroscopy * Surface-enhanced optical spectroscopies *
Radiometry and tissue optics * Photomedicine

Practical trainings

Cell culture preparation & Flow cytometry * Confocal microscopy * Raman spectroscopy
* Optical tweezers & Singlet oxygen detection

Level of study: doctoral

Number of ECTS credits: 8

Košice, May 31, 2023

prof. Pavol Miškovský
director of the School

 This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333